

Effects of Morphology of Organoclay-Modified Epoxy Nanocomposites On Mechanical Performance

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Abstract

The organoclay-modified high performance epoxy nanocomposites were synthesized with a direct-mixing method (DMM) and a high-pressure mixing method (HPMM). X-ray diffraction (XRD) results showed that the organoclay in the nanocomposite fabricated with the DMM are exfoliated or intercalated, but they are not uniformly distributed in the epoxy resin and most of them are in the form of aggregates. The HPMM enhances the degree of exfoliation of the organoclay and breaks up the agglomerates. The mechanical behavior of material formed by these mixing methods was investigated. The organoclay was found to simultaneously improve both fracture toughness and elastic modulus of the epoxy system without decreasing strength. The nanocomposites formed from the HPMM showed dramatic improvement in fracture toughness at very low clay loading; that is, K_{IC} and G_{Ic} were increased by about 2 and 3 times respectively, at 1.5 phr (about 1 wt%) organoclay loading. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) results showed that the glass transition temperature (Tg) of all nanocomposites decreases slightly and the storage modulus increases as the contents of clay increase.

KEY WORDS: Nanocomposites, Epoxy, Morphology, Toughness, Organoclay

1. INTRODUCTION

Although the fiber phase provides most of the strength and stiffness in advanced composites, the matrix phase dominates many key properties such as mechanical properties in hot/wet conditions, toughness, flame resistance and processing versatility *etc.* New technologies for modifying the matrix and synthesizing new materials greatly increased the applications of advanced composites. Recently, nanocomposite technology using organoclay as nanoscale reinforcements offers an interesting alternative for modifying the polymer matrix.

Layered silicate clay is an ideal reinforcement for polymers due to its high aspect ratio, but untreated clay is not easily dispersed in most polymers because of its natural hydrophilicity and incompatibility with organic polymers. Researchers at Toyota^[1] used alkylammonium ions to replace the inorganic cations in the galleries of the clay to synthesize organoclay. The ϵ -Caprolactam was polymerized in the interlayer of an organoclay to form a nanocomposite. This new material showed dramatic improvements in mechanical properties, barrier properties and thermal resistance at lower clay loading as compared with the pristine matrix (pure polymer without clay)^[2-5].

Epoxy nanocomposites have attracted increasing interest from both scientific and industrial perspectives. The formation mechanism and the performance of organoclay-epoxy nanocomposites have been widely

reported [6-12]. According to Pinnavaia [8], organoclay modified epoxies in the rubbery state at room temperature have more effective reinforcement than in the glass state. However, a lot of micro-scale agglomerates were presented in organoclay-epoxy systems although XRD results showed that nanocomposites had been formed [13-16].

The objective of this research was to use the different mixing methods to disperse organoclay in epoxy resin and study the correlation between morphology and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials:

The commercially available organoclay, Nanomer I.30E (Nanacor), is an octadecyl amine modified montmorillonite suitable for dispersion into epoxy resin. Unmodified clay, Cloisite Na⁺ (Southern Clay Product), is a natural montmorillonite. The epoxy resin is N, N, N', N'-tetraglycidyl-4, 4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM), Araldite MY720 and the hardener is 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (DDS), Aradur 976-1(Vantico).

2.2 Sample Preparation:

2.2.1 Direct Mixing Method (DMM):

The clay was dried at 120°C for 2 hrs before mixing. The TGDDM epoxy resin was slowly heated to 110 °C and then the desired amount of hot clay was blown into the resin while stirring. The mixture was held at 110~120 °C and stirred at 1000rpm for 2 hrs, and then degassed in a vacuum oven at 130~135 °C for 30 min followed by sonication at 80°C for 1 hr. At higher clay loadings, the foam of tiny bubbles appeared during degassing and was removed.

2.2.2 High-Pressure Mixing Method (HPMM):

The dry I.30 E clay was dispersed in acetone using the high-pressure mixing machine to form a pasty mixture containing about 10% wt clay (The exact concentration of clay was measured by drying the solution for 8 hrs at 100°C). The desired amount of paste was added to the TGDDM epoxy resin, and the mixture was mixed by hand at room temperature. When the TGDDM was visibly dispersed, the mixture was mechanically stirred at 1000 rpm in a fume hood at room temperature for 30 min, followed by slow heating to 110~120 °C where it was held for 1 hr. Finally, the mixture was degassed under vacuum at 130~135°C for 30 minutes.

2.2.3 Synthesis of Nanocomposites/Filler Composites

The 44 phr (parts per hundred of resin by weight) DDS hardener was dried at 135°C for 1 hr prior to use. The mixture of resin and clay was heated slowly to 135~140°C while stirring. The hot DDS was added into the resin, and then the mixture was mechanically stirred at 1000 rpm for 15 minutes and subsequently degassed at 135~140 °C for 20 minutes. During degassing, foam of tiny bubbles appeared and was removed. The mixture was sonicated at 80 °C for 30 min. and then poured into rubber molds and cured at 135°C/1 hr + 150°C/1.5 hrs and 177°C/2 hrs. The post cure treatment was 200°C/8 hrs.

2.3 Physical Measurement:

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed on a Max 3100 X-ray Generator with Cu radiation (40KV, 20mA). Diffraction was performed from 2° to 12° at a scan rate of 0.96°/min with a step size of 0.02°. The diffracted beam was monochromated before detection. The clay powder and paste containing clay and acetone were placed on a sample holder and a smooth surface was obtained by pressing and scraping the clay with a glass slide. The 25.4 × 25.4 mm square samples of modified epoxies were cut

from 3mm thick plate and their bottom surface was polished with 600[#] grit sand paper. The polished surface was tested.

Dynamic mechanical properties of nanocomposites and filler composites were measured with a TA983 Dynamical Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) in fixed frequency mode at 1Hz with 0.3mm oscillation amplitude, and from 25 °C to 300 °C at 2 °C /min. The sample size is 50 × 12.7 × 3.2 mm³.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images were obtained on a JEOL JSM-840A. SEM was performed on the fracture surfaces after coating with a thin layer of Au/Pd.

Optical micrographs were obtained using an Olympus BH2-UMA Microscope. The area percent of the agglomerates in the matrix was measured using Clemex Image Analysis System Software. The samples were cut from nanocomposites and filler composites and their surfaces were polished.

2.4 Mechanical Measurement:

Compression tests were performed on an MTS809 Axial/ Tensional Test System at a crosshead speed of 2mm/min according to ASTM D695. The compression specimens were cast in the rubber mold and then the upper surface was machined. The size of the compression specimens is 25.4 × 12.7 × 12.7mm³ and at least 5 specimens of each composition were tested.

Fracture tests were performed on an MTS Servo Hydraulic Testing Machine at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min according to ASTM D 5045-99. The single edge notch bending (SENB) specimens including notch were cast from the rubber mold, their upper surfaces were machined, and the specimens were pre-cracked by tapping a fresh razor blade frozen in liquid nitrogen into the notch. The specimen size is 105 × 22 × 7.3mm³ and at least 4 specimens of each composition were tested.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A wide range of the nanocomposites (epoxy with I.30E organoclay) and filler composites (epoxy with Na-montmorillonite clay) were synthesised by the DMM, respectively. The morphology of the cured systems was first investigated using optical microscopy. Like the filler composites, the nanocomposites also contained a lot of agglomerates with the maximum diameter observed being about 20µm (shown in Fig.1 and 2), similarly to that reported by others^[13-16]. Furthermore the size and quantity of agglomerates in the nanocomposites are larger than those in the filler composites at the same clay loading. However, most of the agglomerates of Na-montmorillonite in the filler composites are transparent and have a clear interface with the resin due to its crystal structure. There are no obvious changes in size and quantity of agglomerates for nanocomposites when modifying parameters such as the stirring rate, temperature and time of mixing, or curing parameters.

The mixture of I. 30E and TGDDM epoxy formed by the DMM was carefully examined right after it was prepared in order to determine the formation of agglomerates. Three types of common test methods for determining the dispersion of organoclay were used: the glass slide test, the sedimentation test, and optical microscopy. No agglomerates were seen by holding the two slides containing a drop of mixture up to light and looking through them. No sediment was observed when the mixture was held at 135°C for more than 20 min. But agglomerates were observed under optical microscope when the mixture was diluted with acetone. They are similar to those observed in the cured samples. These results showed that the glass slide test and sedimentation test are not effective to evaluate dispersion, and that the agglomerates in the nanocomposites came from poor dispersion.

The paste of I.30E and acetone mixed by the HPMM was also inspected with optical microscopy. The size and quantity of agglomerates decreased considerably compared with the DMM. Most of the agglomerates are less than 1 μ m and the maximum diameter observed is only 1~2 μ m. This indicated that these agglomerates could be broken down by the HPMM.

Fig. 1. Optical micrograph of modified epoxy containing 6 phr I.30E (DMM)

Fig. 2. Optical micrograph of modified epoxy containing 6 phr Na-montmorillonite (DMM)

The area percentages of agglomerates in the nanocomposites and filler composites are shown in Fig.3. The nanocomposites formed by the DMM have about two times the area of agglomerates as filler composites at the same clay loading as compared to the filler composites. It could be explained that Na-montmorillonite clay was only dispersed by shear forces during mixing, but that the I.30E organoclay has two competing processes: break up and intercalation by resin and hardener. The former decreases the size of agglomerates, but the latter increases the size. However, the materials formed by the HPMM have less agglomerate area because they have better dispersion and most of small particles could not be observed using the optical microscope.

Fig3. Area percentages of agglomerates in nanocomposites and filler composites

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to determine the structure of clay in the nanocomposites and filler composites. Fig. 4 presents the XRD curves of Na-montmorillonite and its composites at different clay

loadings. In the curve for the clay powder without epoxy, a prominent peak corresponding to the basal spacing of Na-montmorillonite occurs at 1.22 nm. At lower clay loadings in epoxy, the prominent peaks shift slightly and the basal spacing of composites with 3phr clay and 6phr clay increases from 1.22 nm to 1.56nm and 1.57nm, respectively. This indicates that a small quantity of resin was forced into the galleries of the clay. However, as the clay loading increases, the basal spacing of Na-montmorillonite in the filler composites falls back to the original value as that of pure clay.

Fig. 4. The XRD patterns of Na-montmorillonite and its composites with DMM

Fig. 5. The XRD patterns of I.30E organoclay and its nanocomposites with DMM

The XRD curves of I.30E organoclay and its nanocomposites using the DMM are shown in Fig. 5. In the curve of I.30E organoclay, the prominent peak corresponding to the basal spacing of I.30E can be seen to be at 2.37 nm. In contrast to the filler composites, the prominent peaks are absent in the curves for most

of the nanocomposites, confirming the formation of exfoliated nanocomposites. The remnant shoulder and small peak in some curves indicate the presence of intercalated nanocomposites. Therefore the organoclays in the nanocomposite with the DMM are exfoliated or intercalated (as shown from XRD data), but they are not uniformly distributed in the epoxy resin and most of them are aggregated on the micro scales as shown from the micrographs.

Fig. 6 shows that the XRD curves of I.30 E organoclay and its nanocomposites with the HPMM. The basal spacing of clay increases from 2.37 nm to 3.22 nm when the I.30 E organoclay with acetone was treated with the HPMM. There are no peaks in the XRD curves of the nanocomposites containing 1.5phr and 3phr I.30E, and their curves are similar to those of TGDDM-DDS system. As a result, the HPMM enhances the degree of exfoliation of organoclay and breaks up the agglomerates of organoclay.

Fig. 6: The XRD Patterns of I.30 E and its nanocomposites with HPMM

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was used to measure the glass transition temperature (T_g) of all nanocomposites and filler composites (shown in Fig.7). In this figure, the T_g of nanocomposites with the DMM decreases slightly with increasing the clay loading in contrast to the filler composites. The reduction in T_g was found to be in the order $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the nanocomposite at 15phr organoclay loading. However, the T_g of nanocomposites with the HPMM decreases very little and is higher than that with DMM at the same clay loading. There are several explanations for this reduction of T_g : the organoclay catalyzes the homopolymerization of the TGDDM resin during the mixing stage and hence changes the network of the cured epoxy. Surface modifiers, or small molecules from thermal degradation of surface modifier at high temperature may exist in the system. The storage modulus at 50°C of all nanocomposite and filler composites increases with increasing clay loading (shown in Fig. 8). However the benefit for nanocomposite is greater than for the filler composites.

Figures 9 and 10 show the compressive yield strength and modulus of nanocomposites and filler composites with clay loading. Both nanocomposites and filler composites have little improvement in compressive yield strength. At lower clay loadings, less than 3 phr and 6 phr respectively for filler composites and nanocomposites, the strength increases, but it decreases with increasing the clay loading above this value. In contrast to other reports ^[4,6,17], nanocomposites have slightly lower yield strength than filler composites. However the modulus improvement of nanocomposites are substantially higher than

those of filler composites. There is a more than 20% increase in modulus of TGDDM-DDS at 9 phr organoclay loading but only a 10% increase for untreated clay.

Fig. 7 The glass transition temperature (Tg) of all nanocomposites and filler composites

Fig. 8 The storage modulus at 50°C of all nanocomposite and filler composites

Fig. 9. The compressive yield strength of nanocomposite and filler composites

Fracture toughness of nanocomposites and filler composites were measured with single-edge-notch bending (SENB). Both critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) and critical strain energy release rate (G_{Ic}) of nanocomposites and filler composites with clay loading are shown in Figures 12 and 13 respectively. The nanocomposite with the DMM shows a higher increase in both K_{IC} and G_{Ic} than the filler composites with increasing clay loading. It shows more than 79% and 151% increase respectively, in K_{IC} and G_{Ic} of TGDDM-DDS with 12 phr organoclay loading but only a 36% and 66% increase for untreated clay. The

nanocomposite with HPMM shows dramatic improvement in fracture toughness at very low clay loading; that is, K_{IC} and G_{IC} were increased by 2 and 3 times respectively, at only 1.5 phr (about 1 wt%) organoclay loading.

Fig.10. The compressive modulus of nanocomposite and filler composites with clay loading

Fig.11. The critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) of nanocomposites and filler composites

The fracture surfaces of the samples were observed using SEM (Fig 13). The pristine resin samples show characteristically smooth surfaces representing brittle failure in a homogenous material (shown in Fig.13A). Fig 13B shows the fracture surface of filler composites at 6phr clay loading. There are agglomerates visible and the maximum diameter is about 20 μ m. The particles are debonded from the resin and voids are formed around the particles. Small number of shallow “ rivers ” around the particles are observed running in the direction of crack propagation. Fig.13C shows fracture surfaces of nanocomposites with DMM at 6phr clay loading. There are also agglomerates visible and the maximum diameter is about 30 μ m for these nanocomposites which is larger than that in filler composites. Only part

Fig. 12. The critical strain energy release rate (G_{1c}) of nanocomposites and filler composites

Fig. 13 SEM micrographs of fracture surface

- A: pristine TGDDM+DDS;
- B: filler composites at 6phr Na-montmorillonite clay;
- C: Nanocomposite with DMM at 6phr I.30 E organoclay;
- D: Nanocomposite with HPMM at 1.5phr I.30 E organoclay.

of the interfaces are debonded from the resin and less void is formed. More and deeper “rivers” around agglomerates are observed. Fig 13D shows the fracture surface of a nanocomposite with HPMM. There are no distinct agglomerates observed on this micrograph and even at relatively high magnification ($\times 10000$). The crack bifurcation is quite evident in this higher magnification image ($\times 20000$) and this is associated with the presence of very small particles which are assumed to be the dispersed clay. Other techniques (possibly TEM) will be required to resolve these particles in more detail. However it is evident that the incorporation and progressively better dispersion of the clay in the resin results in a considerable change in fracture behavior of this resin.

4. CONCLUSION

The organoclays in the nanocomposite formed with DMM are exfoliated or intercalated from XRD data, but they are not uniformly distributed in the epoxy resin and most of them are aggregated on the micro scale. This kind of nanocomposite shows a higher toughness and modulus than filler composites. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of nanocomposites decreases slightly as the content of clay increases. The HPMM enhances the degree of exfoliation of organoclay and breaks up the agglomerates of organoclay. The nanocomposites with HPMM showed dramatic improvement in fracture toughness at very low clay loading; that is, K_{1C} and G_{1C} were increased by 2 and 3 times respectively at 1.5 phr (about 1 wt%) organoclay loading over the pristine resin properties. .

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